

Role of National Directorate of Employment in Curbing Unemployment in Edo State (2012 – 2023)

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Abstract

The study examined the role of national directorate of employment in curbing unemployment in Nigeria with particular reference to Edo State within the time frame of 2012 to 2022. Unemployment is one of the developmental problems that face every developing economy in this twenty-first century, and Nigeria is not exempted. The origin of unemployment in Nigeria can be traced back to the oil boom era of 1970s. The study examined if the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) has well-articulated programmes able to curb unemployment rate in Edo State; ascertain if the NDE is able to maintain data bank on employment in view of reducing the rate of unemployment in Edo State; and examine the challenges facing the NDE in its bid to curb the unemployment rate in Edo State. This study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study include the total number of persons living of Edo state which according to the National Population Commission (2006) is 3,233,366. The method of data analysis used for the purpose of this study was the simple percentage (%) and the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. The study discovered amongst others that there is a significant relationship between the NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State. It recommended amongst others that NDE should imbibe the culture of maintaining an up to date data on unemployment, and NDE should engage in rigorous public sensitization of its plans and programs.

Keywords: Unemployment, National Directorate of Employment, empowerment, skills development

Introduction

The growing unemployment in Nigeria and its concomitant consequences constitute a serious challenge to the economic development with negative effect for future generation, especially as the youths are mostly affected. Nigeria is bedeviled with a myriad of problems, which despite her oil wealth, inhibits her development. The situation has been on the increase over the years, and this has resulted in increase in social vices in the country. Available records clearly show that in the last two decades of the independence of Nigeria as a sovereign nation (1960s and 1970s), unemployment and its attendant consequences, has resulted in poverty, which has become a national concern (Popoola and

Ajayi, 2016). The National Bureau of Statistics (2006) reported that the demand for employment opportunities in the country is ever-increasing with demand clearly outstripping supply.

In the 60's and 70's, the Nigerian government abandoned skills acquisition and utilization through diversified entrepreneurship practices that have the capacity to boost individuals and the country's ego (Akpanung, 2003). Emphasis shifted from entrepreneurial practices to paper qualification which resulted in increased unemployment in the country. The average rates of unemployment in Nigeria during this period were about 2.0%, and 4.5%, respectively (National Bureau of Statistics, 2006). Since, the early 1980s, unemployment in Nigeria has been one of the most menacing social and economic problems the country has had to contend with. For instance, in 1985, the national unemployment rate was 8.5% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2006). Hardly can one find a family (whether rural or urban) in which nobody is either unemployed or threatened by unemployment. Oaikhena (2021) observes that, "...development programmes geared towards humanitarian services need to be a win-win, thereby improving the management and distribution of economic resources and contributing more effectively, as the situation demands".

Unemployment is partly responsible for social ills in the country, such as armed robbery, destitution, prostitution and other social vices (Obike *et al.*, 2007). The latest unemployment figure in Nigeria according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2020) is 18.8% which when translated into labour, means that more than 18 million able-bodied Nigerians are unemployed. More than 70% of the unemployed persons are relatively unskilled, primary and secondary school leavers between the ages of 13 and 25 years; also, graduate unemployment which hitherto was unnoticed, emerged and began to grow rapidly. This situation was quite disturbing to the government, considering the socio-political implications as well as the economic wastage that could result. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2023) posits that "...this type of interventions is necessary because of the vindictiveness of some employers who would do everything possible to take their 'pound of flesh' from the employee for daring to make them lose production hours not minding the right of the workers".

There is a large population of out-of-school youths who are unemployed in Nigeria. In 2008, the then Vice Chancellor of the University of Maiduguri expressed that a total of 90 universities in Nigeria turning out thousands of graduates each year, who eventually go into the job market to seek for the non-existent jobs thereby compounding the unemployment situation with its attendant social challenges (Adebisi & Oni, 2012). Resultantly, the lack of employment has created different platforms for criminal behaviours for some Nigerian university graduates and school leavers. Long-term unemployment has become a feature of the Nigerian labour market, i.e., five years after graduating, many youths are in the labour market in search of jobs that are not available, thereby lending force to crimes, such as armed robbery, car snatching, pipeline vandalization, oil bunkering, and prostitution among others (Adebisi and Oni, 2012).

Available information by National Universities Commission (NUC, 2004) reiterated that the massive unemployment of Nigerian universities graduates in the country is traceable to the disequilibrium between labour market requirements and lack of essential employable skills by the graduates (Emeh 2012).

Therefore, policies and programmes that help to increase employment opportunities will assist in alleviating poverty, since the issue of unemployment has been linked directly to poverty. For the simple reason that the rising rate of unemployment in the country cannot be ignored, the federal government of Nigeria decided to stem the tide by establishing a directorate that will address this serious social-economic challenge; hence the establishment of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in 1986. The fundamental reason for the establishment of the NDE by the federal government

was a committee report which highlighted that the informal sector of the nation's economy had operators and employees who were low skilled, semi-skilled and/or unskilled (Ukoha *et al.* 2014). This group was said to constitute about 90 percent of the workforce within the sector (Ukoha *et al.* 2014). That situation, therefore, placed skills acquisition/training on the front burner with respect to employment creation. This was predicated on the effects of the economic recession of the '80s, which led to drastic reductions in capacity utilization and outright closure of industries in Nigeria.

Similarly, macro-economic policies of government resulted in massive job losses in both the public and private sectors of the economy. As a result of the socio-economic significance of employment creation and the reduction of unemployment to the nation's economy, many research works relating to the various activities of the National Directorate of Employment had been conducted and reported (Akpansung, 2003; Obike *et al.*, 2007; Adebisi and Oni, 2012; Ukoha *et al.* 2014; Ugoani and Ibeenwo, 2015; Anyebe, 2016; Popoola and Ajayi, 2016). The law establishing the NDE presents its mandate from which it derives its routine functions. The main goal, therefore, is to combat mass unemployment through skills acquisition, job creation, self-employment and labour - intensive work schemes (Ugoani and Ibeenwo, 2015). These challenging circumstances required the Federal government of Nigeria to develop and empower the Nigerian youths to enable them contribute effectively to national economic growth. The government adopted strategic plans, programmes and initiated policies through their main institutions for employment and wealth creation; National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and other relevant agencies, in engaging the youths positively with skill development, acquisition, and empowerment packages that will explore their potentials and make them self-reliant. Analysis indicates that unemployment in Nigeria is on the increase and only youth development and empowerment can mitigate this problem.

Problems Associated with Unemployment

From the time immemorial, as asserted by Bello (2003), the subject of unemployment has always been an issue of great concern to policy makers, administrators and economic managers alike, giving the devastating effect of this phenomenon on individuals, the society, and the economy at large. In the 1960's and 1970's, the Nigerian economy provided jobs for the teeming population. The economy also absorbed considerable imported labour in the scientific sectors. The wage rate compared favourably with international standards. There was also relative industrial peace in most industries and some groups. Specifically, following the oil boom of the 1970's, there was rapid migration, especially by the youths to the urban areas in search of wage employment. But following the downturn in the economy in the 1980's, the problem of unemployment started to manifest (Mbah & Agu, 2007).

Successive governments in Nigeria had adopted various policies to create jobs and reduce unemployment in the country. In spite of various employment programmes of successive governments in Nigeria, unemployment rate has continued to rise unabated. This has necessitated the need to undertake this study with a view to assessing and determining the extent to which the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) has proved effective in curbing unemployment in Edo State of Nigeria. Hence, the following questions became necessary; Do the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) have a well-articulated programme to curb unemployment rate in Edo State? Has the NDE able to maintain data bank on employment in view of reducing the rate of unemployment in Edo State? Is there any collaboration between NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in a bid to curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State? What are the challenges facing the NDE in its bid to curbing unemployment in Edo State? The scope of the study is situated within the environment of Edo State of Nigeria and in relation to unemployment within the time frame of 2012 – 2023.

National Directorate of Employment: Scope and Historical Perspective.

The National Manpower Board was directed in 1986 to conduct a sample survey of the unemployed youth, the result was frightening (some 2, 000, 000 unemployed youths or 10%) and this led to the inauguration of Chukwuma Committee in the same year to devise some strategies to combat mass unemployment (Anyebe, 1998). To curb the unemployment, the Babangida administration in 1986 established the National Directorate of Employment, and its programmes were launched nationwide the following year. The Directorate was statutorily mandated to: design and implement programmes to combat mass unemployment; articulate policies aimed at developing work programmes with labour intensive potentials; obtain and maintain a Data Bank on employment and vacancies in the country with a view to acting as a clearing house to link job seekers with vacancies in collaboration with other government agencies; and implement any other policies as may be laid down from time to time by the Board established under sections of the enabling ACT.

In order to actualize its mandate, Gbosi (2005) highlighted that the Directorate launched four well-articulated programmes in 1987. These are: National Youth Employment Programmes; Small scale Industrialist and Graduate Employment Programmes; Special Works Programme; and Agricultural Programme. The programmes were backed by necessary administrative, monitoring and support personnel, thus enabling optimum use of resources and prompt response to the requirements of the public as posited by Amupitan (2007). Toluwalase and Omoniji (2013) highlighted that in 1996, the core employment generation programmes of the NDE were re-organised into: Vocational skills Development (VSD) Programme; Small Scale Enterprise (SSE) Programme; Special Public Works (SPW) Programme; and Rural Employment Promotion (REP) Programme.

However, from 8.5% in 1985, the unemployment rate in the country rose to 11.9 % in 2005, 12.7 % in 2007, 14.9 % in 2008, 19.7 % in 2009, 21.4 % in 2010, and 23.9 % in 2011. Undoubtedly, those who feel the brunt of the unemployment crisis in Nigeria the most are the youths. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2012) 54 % of Nigerian youths were unemployed in 2012. In the “2012 National Baseline Youth Survey Report” issued by NBS in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Youth Development in December 2013, it was reported that more than half, about 54 % of the youth population were unemployed. Of this, females stood at 15.9 % compared to their male counterpart with 48.1%.” The survey classified youth to be those between ages of 15 and 35. According to the survey, the population of youths aged 15 to 35 years in Nigeria is estimated to be 64million. The youth unemployment crisis in Nigeria is so severe that over 100,000 youths sometimes jostle for 25 vacancies as pointed out by Durotoye (2014).

The nation (2016) reported that the newly launched jobs portal of the Federal Government “NPower.gov.ng” recorded over 400, 000 successful registrations within 36 hours after opening for 500, 000 teaching job positions. NBS states that the rate of unemployment among economically active Nigerians between the youthful ages of 15-24 was as high as 37.7 % in 2011 while among those within the age bracket of 25-44 years, the unemployment rate was 22.4 %. For Nigerians within the age of 45 and 59, the rate of unemployment stood at 18.0 % while it was 21.4 % among those within the age bracket of 60 and 64. The translation of this is that Nigerians between the youthful ages of 15 and 24 are those mostly affected by unemployment and are, as such, more vulnerable to its attendant consequences. This evidence is collaborated by the World Bank (2016) which reports that the unemployment rate among Nigerians between the ages of 15-24 was 13.8 % in 2011; 13.7 % in 2012; 13.6 % in 2013; and 13.6 % in 2014.

The importance attached to NDE in Nigeria can be seen from the fact that with the end of the military rule in 1999, the Directorate was given legal backing, with its continued existence guaranteed by its enabling ACT, CAP250 of the laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. However, in spite of its

continued operation and financing (for example, the NDE was allocated N5,905,302,638 in the 2016 budget), the unemployment rate in Nigeria keeps rising. What is responsible for this state of affairs? It is against this backdrop that the researcher poses this research question: what have been the achievements and the challenges of the NDE since its establishment in 1986. As highlighted above, the NDE utilizes four major programmes as vehicles of combating unemployment and they are: **a)** National Youth Employment and Vocational Skills Development Programme **b)** Small Scale Industries and Graduate Employment Programme, **c)** Agricultural Sector Employment Programme and **d)** Special Public Works Programme.

National Youth Employment and Vocational Skills Development Programmes

This programme takes care of the majority of Nigerian Youths who have no productive and marketable skills. The programme is run through the national open apprenticeship scheme, waste to wealth scheme, schools on wheels scheme and disabled work scheme. Under the programme the participants are required to register with the Federal Ministry of Employment, Labour and Productivity's local labour exchanges before being accepted as trainees when they have completed their period of apprenticeship thereby acquiring the necessary skills, they become potential candidates for employer's consideration and absorption. Alternatively, those who can go into self-employment are encouraged to do so.

According to Ogundele, Akingbade, and Akinlabi (2012), the contribution of Skill Acquisition and training on unemployment reduction through youth empowerment and social welfare service improvement will be much significant if encouraged at all the levels in the state especially at local and community levels. This position consolidates on Ohize and Muhammed (2009), who opined that non-governmental organization can play a vital role in training and skill acquisition. This is evident from the success story of project YES as findings revealed that the scheme has contributed to the economic uplift of the youths by providing them with vocational skills and counseling services aimed at reorienting their attitudes towards self and societal development.

Akpama *et al* (2011) observed that acquisition of vocational skills lead to a significant reduction of poverty among young adults who participated on skills acquisition programmes. Entrepreneurial studies are inter-disciplinary training that focuses on the tools needed to start a new business or vocation, because Nigeria is fast becoming a predominantly youthful society with high rate of Unemployment. It requires training the youth in entrepreneurship skills in technical vocational education and training to tackle unemployment which has reached alarming proportions. Amadi and Abdullah (2012), reported from their study that a greater percentage of the sampled youth reported high and moderate levels of their capacity building: implying that the vocational skills acquisition and development was a successful scheme. They however recommended that the constraints that impede the success of the scheme be addressed by policy makers to make the outcome of the skills training more successful.

Adofu and Ocheja (2013) investigated the conduct of skill acquisition and training in alleviating poverty and unemployment in Kogi state, Nigeria. This relationship between entrepreneurship skill acquisition and poverty/unemployment was analyzed using descriptive statistics to test the validity or otherwise of the effect of entrepreneurship skill acquisition on poverty alleviation and unemployment reduction in Nigeria using primary data obtained in six local government areas that made up the four districts of the state. The result shows that 65% of the respondents accepted that lack of entrepreneurship skills among youth is responsible for the high rate of poverty/unemployment in Nigeria. The result also revealed that at least 60% of the people that benefitted from the skills acquisition programme can now afford the basic necessity of life. The study, therefore, recommended

that since most of the people that benefited from the programme could afford the basic necessity of life, the government should begin to think of the way of developing the programme to the status of poverty/unemployment eradication programme. More often than not, some Scholars focuses on Skill Acquisition enshrine in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship skills acquired in the context of this study refers to an individual's knowledge and ability to perform specific tasks successfully; while entrepreneurship according to Anerua and Obiazi (2009) is the process of perceiving business opportunities, mobilizing both human and material resources and initiating action(s) under an enterprise which is characterized by risk taking, innovation and creativity to meet individual, group or societal needs.

Entrepreneurship skills therefore, are business skills which one acquires to function effectively in the turbulent business environment as an independent or self-employed person in order to improve one's economic status and the society at large. The importance of entrepreneurship skills acquisition cannot be over-emphasized since appropriate skills acquisition through entrepreneurship will help to make young school leavers to be self-reliant and boost their economic status. Isike (2008) stated that entrepreneurship has been identified globally and nationally as a tool for generating a sustainable economy which is the core value of the National Economic Empowerment Development Strategies (NEEDS). Through such Skills Acquisition, the establishment of small businesses helps to generate substantial amount of employment and income which are essential parts of a country's Gross National Product (GNP) on the one hand and reduce unemployment on the other. For the laudable benefits of entrepreneurship skills acquisition to manifest in our youth and the general public, skills must be learned through formal or nonformal settings.

Uloko and Ejinkonye (2010) remarked that when youths are empowered through the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills, there is the possibility that they will use the skills to create new avenues for wealth. Empowering the youth to set up businesses involves proper acquisition of skills through education and training. Such acquisition opens one's eyes to forecast business opportunities using appropriate entrepreneurship skills. Okolocha and Okolocha (2012) accepted that students can acquire such entrepreneurial skills from student industrial work experience scheme (SIWES). In a study of such effect in 258 Nigerian students in Anambra State, they found that SIWES is an important programme that can help to bridge the gap between school life and the world of works by blending meaningful job experiences with related institutions learnt in the classroom. For SIWES to help students to acquire the appropriate entrepreneurial skills that will help them face the challenges of unemployment and economic crises, proper machinery for sustained SIWES programme was advocated.

Ola-Adebayo (2013) advocated that this is better achieved through Entrepreneurship Education. In a study of the determinants of Skill Acquisition and professional knowledge acquired by Nigerian graduates through the current university curriculum using primary research techniques, it was found that entrepreneurial education is best received in the school settings. Also, learning by doing is seen as the best approach or method to teach entrepreneurial education. The research also noted that being male or female has nothing to do with perception of the importance of acquiring entrepreneurial skills education within and outside the school system. Employment should be made mandatory on the platform of having gone through any one vocational education training, the study opined. The authority in charge of education should face-up to the challenges and proffer a way out of the dilemma of unemployment which has resulted in insecurity and economic instability in the country. Ezeji and Okorie (1999) while stressing the importance of skills acquisition in national growth, emphatically contended, "that Nigeria's social and economic problems will be drastically reduced if people are given adequate vocational training in skills, raw materials, machineries and equipment". However, Oaikhena (2021) argued that "the governments in sub-Saharan Africa for example do not have enough data and

administrative knowledge, necessary for reliably identifying the poor in the society, which means the countries can't target resources allocated to them".

It is only with skilled men that materials can be harnessed, manipulated and transformed into products. With quality skills acquisition programmes, countries like America, Britain, Germany and Japan have rehabilitated drug addicts, school dropouts and several destitute who eventually contributed meaningfully to the economy and the development of high volume of productivity in their countries. In their study, Kanyenze, et al (2000) underscores that trainings in vocational and technical skills will reduce youth marginalization.

Theoretical Framework

Ndebio's Theory of industrialization

Ndebio (1987), theorized that the hope for employment creation lies in industrialization and it is possible to industrialize a nation through the creation and promotion of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) and Rural Development Programmes (RDPs). He asserted that it is the need for employment generation and economic growth that explains the essence of promoting SMEs in Nigeria to help in absorbing the rapid growing labour force.

This is specifically important in developing countries like Nigeria where labour is abundant and capital relatively scarce. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE), which is the case study of this paper, agrees to the theory as the Directorate, on inception, was saddled with the responsibility to tackle employment problems in both the short and long term perspectives by formulating and administering job creation as well as employment related training programmes. This is seen in the Directorate's four programme departments, constituting the Vocational Skill Development (VSD), Small Scale Enterprises (SSE), Rural Employment Promotion (REP) and Special Public Works (SPW) departments whose resultant effort is to employ more labour perhaps of low skill category given the same size of capital investment used in creating large scale industry. This incidentally agrees with the observation of little (1987) that right from the 1960's, SMEs were believed to offer much more employment than larger firms for any given investment. Also, in the 1988 census of business conducted in Nigeria by the Federal Office of Statistics (FOS), SMEs were estimated to have constituted about 70 per cent of the 220,000 industrial establishments surveyed and accounted for 70 per cent of industrial employment as well as 10-15 per cent of manufacturing output (Damachi, 2001).

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted the survey research design. The adoption of the survey research design in this study made the study explorative as well as descriptive in nature.

Population of Study

According to Schutt (1999), research population is the sum total of all the elements of units of analysis which a study is interested in. The population of the study includes the total number of persons living in Edo state which according to the National Population Commission (2006) is 3,233,366, which comprises both officials of NDE and beneficiaries of NDE programmes and schemes.

Sampling Technique

This research work adopted the probability sampling as its sampling technique for which the selection of the sample to be under-studied was based on chance. This chance selection ensures that every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected or represented in the sample.

Sampling Size

In arriving at the sample size, the random sampling method was adopted in this study. The reason for using the random sampling method is to ensure that every member of the population has an equal opportunity of being selected. From the 18 local government areas in Edo state, 20 beneficiaries of NDE programmes were selected as sampled respondents making a total of 340 while 20 staff (senior and junior staff) were also selected from the NDE, Edo State, making the study sample size to be 360.

Sources of Data

Basically, there are two major sources of data collection utilized in this study. They are: **Primary Sources**: This entails gathering information through the administration of questionnaires which was structured in line with the relevant objectives of the study, while the **Secondary Sources** involves the use of data from sources such as published books, journals, Newspapers, magazines, as well as internet sources.

Instrument of Data Collection

The research instrument for the collection of data for this study was the use of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured in two sections that is, sections A and B. Section A dwelled on the socio-demographic profile of the surveyed as age, educational qualification, occupational distribution and religion. Section B covers issues that are related to the objectives of the study. The questions were structured along the close-ended response pattern, where respondents were given options to choose from.

Techniques for Data Analysis

The method of data analysis used for this study was the simple percentage (%) and the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. The simple percentage was used to analyze the data collected through the questionnaire, while the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was used to analyzed the research hypotheses via the SPSS 21.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

1. Ho: There is no significant relationship between NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State.

Table 1: Correlation between NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State.

		Correlations	
		NDE Programme s	Unemploymen t Rate
NDE Programmes	Pearson Correlation	1	.836**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Unemploye nt Rate	Pearson Correlation	.836**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 reveals that, there exist a significant relationship between NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State with a correlation coefficient *R* value of 0.836, indicating that, NDE programmes has a very strong influence on unemployment rate in Edo State. Furthermore, with the *p*-value (Sig = 0.000) less than (<) 0.01, the study thus rejects the null hypothesis (there is no significant relationship between NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State) and accept the research hypothesis (there is a significant relationship between NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State).

Hypothesis Two

2. Ho: There is no significant relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State.

Table 2: Correlation between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State.

		Correlations	
		NDE Data Bank on Employment	Unemployment Reduction
NDE Data Bank on Employment	Pearson Correlation	1	.751**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Unemploye nt Reduction	Pearson Correlation	.751**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Data from table 2 shows a significant relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State. With a correlation coefficient value of 0.751, the table above reveals a very strong correlation between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in

the rate of unemployment in Edo State. The study rejects the null hypothesis (there is no significant relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State) due the *p*-value (sig = 0.000) less than 0.01, and accept the research hypothesis (there is a significant relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State).

Hypothesis Three

3. Ho: There is no significant relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State.

Table 3: Correlation between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State.

Correlations			
		Collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO)	Unemployment Reduction
Collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO)	Pearson Correlation	1	.893**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Unemployment Reduction	Pearson Correlation	.893**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 analysis reveals a positive relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State, due to the high rate of *R* coefficient which is 0.893, hence signifying a strong relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State. The data from table 24 also reveals a *p*-value (sig = 0.000) which is < 0.01, indicating that the researcher rejects the null hypothesis which state that, there is no significant relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State, and accepts the research hypothesis which states that, there is a significant relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State.

Hypothesis Four

4. Ho: There is no significant relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State.

Table 25: Correlation between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State.

Correlations		
	Challenges facing NDE	Unemployment Rate

Challenges facing NDE	Pearson Correlation	1	.909**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Unemployment Rate	Pearson Correlation	.909**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 reveals that, there exist a significant relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State with a correlation coefficient R value of 0.904, indicating that, the challenges facing the NDE has a strong influence on unemployment rate in Edo State. Furthermore, with the p -value (Sig = 0.000) less than ($<$) 0.01, the study thus rejects the null hypothesis (there is no significant relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State) and accept the research hypothesis (there is a significant relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State).

Discussion of Findings

This study undertaken examined the role of NDE in curbing unemployment in Edo state, Nigeria. The main goal of this study was to assess the challenges facing NDE in its role of curbing unemployment in Nigeria. Having subjected the data collected from the respondents to statistical package for social science (SPSS), the outcome of the research revealed the following findings which include.

Firstly, this study examined the relationship between the NDE and unemployment rate. The study revealed that the activities of NDE had an impact on the unemployment rate in Edo, Nigeria

The activities of the NDE in Edo state has been seen to impact on the unemployment rate in the state. The NDE's activities in the skilled, unskilled and semi-skilled job sectors which have impacted on the unemployment rate as indicated from the respondents. Other scholars also express this point of views. Toluwalase & Omoniji (2013) in their theoretical analysis pointed out that youth population is increasing explosively particularly in developing countries as a result of rapid urbanization. The continuous decrease in the manufacturing employment has made many of the young people facing three options: getting jobs in the informal economy with insecurity and poor wages and working conditions, getting jobs in the low-tier service industries, or developing their vocational skills to benefit from new opportunities in the professional and advanced technical/knowledge sectors. Moreover, in developing countries, like Nigeria a large portion of young people are not even lucky enough to choose among any of these options facing as a consequence, long-term unemployment, which makes them highly vulnerable.

This demands that the government must respond through policy interventions in setting institutional framework that will be responsible in enhancing skill, and training to complement the products from different academia. This presupposes that technical and vocational education institutions can respond to the different socio-economic and academic backgrounds and prepare the clientele for gainful employment and sustainable livelihoods. Thus, the youth, the poor and the vulnerable in the society can benefit from vocational/technical education. In other to achieve this target, National Directorate of Employment and few other institutions were created. Adebisi and Oni (2012) advocated that meeting the training needs of the prospective trainees of the National Directorate of Employment

is what makes the training programmes of the Directorate relevant to the plights of the unemployed. To identify and evaluate people's needs, adult educator must understand the nature and role of needs in the training programmes. In their findings, they observed that the NDE has enough schemes and job categories from which the prospective beneficiaries can acquire necessary skills that will guarantee their employment.

The study investigated the relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State. The study revealed that respondents agreed NDE data bank aids in the reduction of the unemployment rate in Edo state. Also, correspondents agreed that NDE engages in periodic data gathering activities. Data gathering is an important aspect of the aim for unemployment reduction as this informs the decision making process of the NDE. The economic and social development of any nation depends to a large extent on the emergency of a strong and vibrant private sector driven by entrepreneurship and respondents of this study agree that the entrepreneurship activities of the NDE has an impact on the unemployment rate, in fact they say it has led to a reduction. This opinion is supported by realities on ground as the NDE has several initiatives by the government to foster the creation of more micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs), strengthen the management capacity of the existing institutions and working out some modalities to provide easy access to capital for entrepreneurship development. The agency believes that the ebb and flow of any meaningful business enterprise is usually highly dependent on the resilience of entrepreneurial activity often measured by an extraordinary predisposition to business venturing, the manifestation of high spirit for exceptional financial risk appetite, and a natural interest to the pursuit of productive investment and Akpama, Esang, Asor, and Osang (2011) also believes is the basis of entrepreneurship.

The study also sought to explain the relationship between NDE and the Bank of Industry (BOI) in a bid to curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State. The respondents generally agreed that the NDE and BOI had an impact on the rate of unemployment in Edo state. They agreed that programs of the NDE and BOI like small and medium scale enterprises, N-power and rural employment programs had an impact on unemployment rate reduction while undecided if special works program had an impact on the unemployment rate. The primary mandate of Bank of Industry (BOI) is to financially assist the establishment of small, medium and large project as well as expansion, diversification and modernization of existing enterprises and reliability of oiling industries, and to ensure a level playing for domestic businesses to attain international state which have the propensity to ensure better economic growth of the nation (Sanusi, 2013). The role of Bank of Industry is to promote the SMEs across all industries with little or no collateral and low interest charged on finances advanced to such sector (Akingunola, 2011). Central Bank of Nigeria (2011) opined that Bank of Industry (BOI) volume of loan to MSMES have a working capacity facility of one year with provision for roll over or maximum of 15 years and the fund allows for moratorium in the loan repayment schedule. To collaborate this, Bank of Industry (2013) noted that interest charged on credit to SMEs is cost faced by small, medium and large enterprises when borrowing from Bank of Industry though not as the deposit money banks charged. BOI (2013) further opined that low interest rate will help the MSMES to payback and as when due and contribute to economic growth. Opafunso and Adepoju (2014) employed analysis of descriptive statistics and Chi-square tools to investigate the role of small and medium enterprises on economic development of Ekiti state in Nigeria over the data base and discovered there is a positive and significant relationship that exists between small and medium enterprises have significant role and effectiveness on poverty reduction, employment generation and advancement of wellbeing of the citizens in Ekiti State. The study inferred that low interest charged on bank loans has the capacity to improve the performance of small and medium enterprises in Ekiti state and Nigeria at large. A similar study, carried out in Bauchi metropolis by Sama'ila and Tahir (2015) on contribution of the Bank of Industry towards SMEs industrial development, evidently found that Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Bauchi Metropolis significantly benefited from BOI's loans and that the loans

were directed to the right channels. Iloh and Chioke (2015) collated data from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin for the period of 1980 to 2010 to analyze the nexus between commercial bank credit indicators and availability of credit facility to small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria and it revealed that commercial banks' credit to SMEs in Nigeria have significant effect on Nigeria economic growth by positively affecting gross domestic product.

Lastly, the relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate were investigated. The respondents agreed that Mismanagement and corruption are challenges facing the NDE in its role of unemployment rate reduction in Edo state. Mismanagement and corruption is a bane of many public institutions and the NDE is no exception to this. Also lack of funding and regime change also were challenges highlighted by respondents as facing the NDE in its bid to reduce the unemployment rate in Edo state.

Conclusion

From the data collected and analyzed from the field, the study concludes amongst others that, there is a significant relationship between the NDE programmes and unemployment rate in Edo State. Also, the study discovered a positive significant relationship between NDE data bank on employment and reduction in the rate of unemployment in Edo State. The study also concluded that there is a significant relationship between the collaboration of NDE and the Bank of Industry (BIO) in curbing the rate of unemployment in Edo State. and lastly there also exist a positive relationship between the challenges facing the NDE and the unemployment rate in Edo State.

Recommendations

The findings of the study have provided vital information about the role of NDE in curbing unemployment in Nigeria: A case study of Edo state, Nigeria. It is based on the findings of this study that the following recommendations were made:

1. NDE should imbibe the culture of maintaining an up to date repository on unemployment.
2. NDE should engage in rigorous public sensitization of its plans and programs.
3. NDE programs should be designed to reflect the current world realities ie tech, soft skills acquisition.
4. Successive regimes should maintain the template and programs of previous administrations.
5. Adequate fundings for NDE activities should be a top priority for government.

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